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Kopi: Slette-meås, Jannice Schau; PERRIN-GUYOMARD Agnes; Kees Veldman (Kees.Veldman@wur.nl);
Stefan Börjesson
Emne: IMPART WP1 and WP2 Ring trials : planning

Dear IMPART partners,

After consulting you several times over the last weeks, we think we have come to a final planning.

Planning those ring trials are a bit difficult with all the bank holidays in the different participating countries before summer holidays.

As our samples have to be fresh, we need to find a window of 2 consecutive weeks were a full team is

present in our lab at Anses to prepare the contaminated samples, ship them and test them for stability

and homogeneity in the same timeline than the participants.

WP1 trial : planned on week 25. Shipment of the samples is planned to leave France on Monday, June 17th

You are supposed to receive the samples on Tuesday, June 18th.

Labs who agreed to participate will receive very shortly a draft protocol and a questionnaire to make sure you are ready in time to participate and what should be provided to you.

WP2 trial : originally planned week 22 has been postponed to week 37 as too many participants were having bank holidays on week 22.

Shipment of the samples is planned to leave France on Monday, September 9th. You are supposed to receive the samples on Tuesday, September 10th.

Participants would also receive within the next weeks with detailed information about this WP2 trial.

Best wishes,

Agnes, Jannice, Kees and Sophie